

CRISPR-Based Biosensors for Pathogen Detection: Current Status and Future Potential

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CRISPR (Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats) technology is a promising tool to meet the needs of detecting infectious diseases in a rapid, sensitive, and specific manner. CRISPR was discovered in bacterial and archaeal cells as an adaptive defense system against phage infections or mobile genetic elements. Early, rapid, and accurate pathogen detection is essential for disease diagnosis, surveillance, and outbreak control. Traditional diagnostic methods, while reliable, often require complex instrumentation, trained personnel, and extended turnaround times. The advent of (CRISPR)-based biosensing systems has revolutionized the field of molecular diagnostics, enabling rapid, specific, and cost-effective detection of pathogenic microorganisms. This review explores the current state of CRISPR-based biosensors, their mechanisms, integration with nucleic acid amplification and microfluidic systems, and their potential in point-of-care (POC) diagnostics. Finally, the article discusses challenges and emerging prospects for clinical translation and global health applications.

Keywords: CRISPR, Biosensors, Pathogen, Emerging, SHERLOCK.

INTRODUCTION

Pathogenic microorganisms remain a major cause of global morbidity and mortality, with infectious diseases accounting for significant public health and economic burdens worldwide. Traditional diagnostic techniques such as culture, polymerase chain reaction (PCR), and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA) have provided critical insights into pathogen detection; however, their reliance on laboratory infrastructure limits rapid field deployment, especially in low-resource settings (Razavi et al., 2024). Recent advances in molecular biology and synthetic biology have led to the development of CRISPR-based biosensors, offering a powerful platform for rapid, specific, and sensitive detection of pathogens. Initially recognized for their genome-editing potential, CRISPR systems have evolved into robust diagnostic tools through the exploitation of their programmable nucleic acid recognition and

collateral cleavage activities (Pardee et al., 2016). Originally identified in bacteria and archaea as an adaptive immune mechanism that defends against bacteriophage infections and mobile genetic elements, CRISPR systems have since been extensively studied.

In 2012, researchers demonstrated for the first time that the CRISPR/Cas9 complex could precisely cleave DNA *in vitro*, a landmark achievement that revolutionized genetic research and paved the way for its broad application in genome editing and therapeutic development (Jinek et al., 2012).

Principle of CRISPR-Based Biosensing

Cas effectors exhibit remarkable diversity and are broadly categorized into two main groups: Class I CRISPR systems, which utilize multiple Cas proteins working together, and Class II systems, which rely on a single multifunctional Cas protein to perform their defensive and catalytic functions (Makarova et al., 2011, Makarova et al., 2020). Apart from a limited number of nucleic acid

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detection approaches utilizing the Class I CRISPR system (Gootenberg et al., 2018, Santiago-Frangos et al., 2021), most biosensing strategies are based on the Class II CRISPR system due to its simpler assembly process and superior operational efficiency. Within the Class II CRISPR systems, Cas9, Cas12, and Cas13 are the most extensively utilized and thoroughly investigated effectors (Shmakov et al., 2015). The Cas9 and Cas12 systems function as RNA-guided DNases that identify and cleave target DNA sequences located next to protospacer-adjacent motif (PAM) sites, relying on strong complementarity between the guide RNA and the target DNA. In contrast, the Cas13 system acts as an RNA-guided RNase, recognizing and cleaving RNA solely through the complementarity between the CRISPR RNA (crRNA) and the target RNA, although certain Cas13 variants also require specific protospacer-flanking site (PFS) sequences for activity. Cas14-based systems detect single-stranded DNA with high precision, expanding applications for small viral genomes. This unique cleavage activity generates a detectable signal, typically through fluorescence, colorimetry, or electrochemical readouts (Kellner et al., 2019).

Major CRISPR-Based Diagnostic Platforms:

SHERLOCK (Specific High Sensitivity Enzymatic Reporter Unlocking)

In 2017, Professor Feng Zhang and his team harnessed the unique activity of Cas13a to create an efficient CRISPR-based diagnostic platform called Specific High-Sensitivity Enzymatic Reporter Unlocking (SHERLOCK). The following year, this platform was successfully applied for the rapid detection of infectious diseases, including Zika virus and COVID-19 (Kellner et al., 2019). The SHERLOCK platform integrates nucleic acid pre-amplification with the collateral cleavage activity of Cas13, enabling precise recognition of target nucleic acids. This combination allows for ultrasensitive, portable, and multiplexed detection of pathogenic nucleic acids directly from clinical samples (Mustafa and Makhawi, 2021). The high sensitivity and precision of the SHERLOCK system make it a valuable alternative to PCR-based methods, offering a more cost-effective option for decentralized or field-based diagnostic testing. The SHERLOCK detection process involves three primary stages: (i) sample collection, (ii) target amplification, and (iii) CRISPR-mediated collateral cleavage and signal detection. The procedure begins with sample acquisition, which may include blood, urine, nasal swabs, or extracted nucleic acids (DNA or RNA) from patient specimens. This is followed by isothermal amplification of the target genetic material using techniques such as recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA) or loop-mediated isothermal

amplification (LAMP). SHERLOCK has demonstrated itself as a flexible and reliable tool for detecting both DNA and RNA, with wide-ranging applications in rapid disease diagnostics and genetic profiling. In 2017, SHERLOCK v1 was launched, utilizing the Cas13a nuclease from *Leptotrichia wadei*, which specifically targets and cleaves RNA molecules, unlike Cas12. While SHERLOCK v1 was reliable and capable of detecting low viral loads, its practical use was constrained by its qualitative readout, reliance on fluorescent detection equipment, and limitation to detecting only a single target per reaction. These challenges were overcome in SHERLOCK v2, which introduced several improvements: (i) the combined activity of Cas13 and Csm6, increasing sensitivity by 3.5-fold, (ii) four-channel multiplexing using Cas enzyme orthologs to detect up to four targets in a single reaction, (iii) quantitative signal measurement, and (iv) lateral flow readouts for portable, instrument-free detection. The Cas13–Csm6 combination not only enhances sensitivity but also enables direct detection of most pathogen variants without pre-amplification. These advancements expanded the platform's quantitative capabilities and practical utility, making detection more visual, sensitive, and versatile.

DETECTR (DNA Endonuclease-Targeted CRISPR Trans Reporter)

DETECTR operates by activating the Cas12a protein once it recognizes its target DNA, enabling it to cleave nearby DNA sequences. In this system, Cas12a and the complementary crRNA are combined with a single-stranded DNA reporter probe and added to the clinical sample. The crRNA binds to the pathogen's nucleic acid sequence, triggering cleavage of the DNA reporter probe and generating a fluorescent signal. During the initial phase, recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA) is performed at a constant temperature to amplify the target sequence, enhancing detection sensitivity without the need for sophisticated or costly instrumentation. One of the most prominent applications of DETECTR is its ability to detect and genotype human papillomavirus (HPV) in infected cell lines or clinical specimens¹². The technology can accurately identify high-risk HPV infections, achieving detection rates of 100% for HPV16 and 92% for HPV18, which is critical for assessing the risk of HPV-related cancers. Additionally, Jianhao and colleagues developed a DETECTR-based method for detecting *Bacillus anthracis*, demonstrating that it is highly sensitive, rapid, and specific. This suggests that DETECTR could potentially be applied for the detection of *Bacillus anthracis* in the future (Xuet al., 2023).

HOLMES and HOLMESv2

In 2018, HOLMES (One-Hour Low-cost Multipurpose Highly Efficient System) was introduced as a Cas12a-

based CRISPR diagnostic platform for rapid and sensitive nucleic acid detection (Li et al., 2018). The system exploits the collateral cleavage activity of Cas12a, which, upon recognizing a specific DNA sequence, indiscriminately cuts nearby single-stranded DNA reporters, resulting in a fluorescent signal that enables target visualization. By combining this activity with polymerase chain reaction (PCR) or isothermal amplification techniques such as recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA), HOLMES achieves rapid, low-cost, and highly specific detection of both DNA and RNA within an hour. Subsequently, an improved version, HOLMESv2, was developed to enhance diagnostic performance. This version employs Cas12b, a thermophilic CRISPR effector that provides greater thermal stability, faster cleavage kinetics, and enhanced specificity compared to Cas12a (Li et al., 2019). HOLMESv2 also supports one-pot reactions by integrating with loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP), minimizing the risk of contamination and simplifying workflow. Together, the HOLMES and HOLMESv2 systems represent highly versatile CRISPR-based biosensing platforms with significant potential for pathogen detection, genotyping, and point-of-care diagnostics.

CRISPR-Chip and Electrochemical Biosensors

The integration of CRISPR systems with electrochemical and field-effect transistor (FET)-based technologies has led to the development of CRISPR-Chip, an innovative platform for amplification-free, real-time nucleic acid detection. The CRISPR-Chip combines a graphene-based transistor with immobilized Cas9–guide RNA complexes to enable the direct electrical detection of specific DNA sequences without the need for target amplification (Hajian et al., 2019).

When the target DNA binds to the Cas9–gRNA complex on the graphene surface, it induces a measurable change in the electrical signal, providing rapid and label-free detection.

This electrochemical biosensing approach offers several advantages, including high sensitivity, specificity, and short detection times, while eliminating the requirement for fluorescent or enzymatic signal readouts. Moreover, the CRISPR-Chip platform has demonstrated the ability to detect unamplified genes associated with genetic diseases such as Duchenne muscular dystrophy, underscoring its clinical potential (Hajian et al., 2019).

Building on this concept, subsequent research integrated other Cas effectors, such as Cas12a and Cas13a, into electrochemical and microfluidic platforms to develop portable, low-cost biosensors suitable for point-of-care pathogen detection (Mohammad et al., 2022, Wang et al., 2025). These systems convert Cas-mediated collateral cleavage events into measurable electrical or colorimetric signals, offering a robust and

field-deployable diagnostic strategy. The merging of CRISPR technologies with nanomaterials and microelectronics is thus paving the way for next-generation biosensors with unprecedented precision and usability in clinical, environmental, and food safety monitoring.

Integration with Point-of-Care (POC) Technologies

The advancement of point-of-care (POC) diagnostic technologies has greatly benefited from the integration of CRISPR-based biosensing systems with portable, low-cost, and user-friendly platforms. These integrations aim to bring molecular diagnostics closer to clinical and field settings, allowing rapid and decentralized testing without the need for complex laboratory infrastructure.

One of the most promising approaches is the combination of CRISPR–Cas systems with isothermal amplification techniques such as recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA) and loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP). These methods enable rapid amplification of nucleic acids at constant temperatures, eliminating the need for thermal cyclers and reducing assay time (Broughton et al., 2020). When coupled with CRISPR-based detection, these isothermal platforms produce highly sensitive and specific results within an hour, suitable for POC diagnostics.

Furthermore, the integration of CRISPR biosensors with lateral flow assays (LFAs) and paper-based microfluidic devices has enabled instrument-free visual detection, expanding accessibility in resource-limited regions (Wang et al., 2025). For instance, Cas12 and Cas13 systems have been adapted for colorimetric readouts, where the cleavage of labeled reporter molecules produces a visible signal detectable by the naked eye. Such platforms were successfully deployed for SARS-CoV-2 detection, demonstrating diagnostic performance comparable to RT-qPCR but with lower cost and faster turnaround time (Patchsung et al., 2020).

Applications of CRISPR-Based Biosensors in Pathogen Detection

CRISPR-based biosensors have demonstrated significant potential across diverse fields of pathogen detection, enabling rapid, precise, and highly sensitive identification of bacterial, viral, parasitic, and fungal pathogens. Their programmability and adaptability make them particularly suited for detecting a wide variety of infectious agents from clinical, environmental, and food samples.

In viral diagnostics, CRISPR platforms such as SHERLOCK, DETECTR, and HOLMES have been extensively applied for the detection of emerging and re-emerging viruses. For instance, the Cas13-based SHERLOCK system has successfully detected Zika virus, Dengue virus, and SARS-CoV-2, achieving attomolar-level sensitivity and single-base specificity (Broughton

et al., 2020, Gootenberg et al., 2017). Similarly, Cas12-based DETECTR assays have been employed for the rapid identification of human papillomavirus (HPV) genotypes and COVID-19, providing results comparable to gold-standard PCR tests but within significantly shorter time frames (Patchesung et al., 2020, Chen et al., 2018).

In bacterial detection, CRISPR–Cas12a and Cas14a systems have been utilized to identify *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Salmonella* spp., among others (Wang et al., 2025). These biosensors enable species-level discrimination and, in some cases, even strain-level typing based on sequence-specific recognition of bacterial genetic markers. CRISPR-based detection has also been integrated into microfluidic paper-based devices for field surveillance of foodborne pathogens, offering portability and rapid response capabilities.

Additionally, the technology has shown promise in parasitic and fungal diagnostics. Cas12a-based biosensors have been applied for detecting *Plasmodium falciparum* DNA in malaria-infected samples, while Cas13a systems have been used for the identification of *Candida albicans* RNA (Aggarwal et al., 2021, Liu et al., 2025). These developments highlight the versatility of CRISPR-based biosensors in addressing global diagnostic needs.

Overall, CRISPR-driven diagnostic platforms offer an unprecedented combination of speed, sensitivity, specificity, and affordability, making them valuable tools for infectious disease diagnosis, epidemiological surveillance, and public health preparedness, especially in low-resource environments

Advantages of CRISPR-Based Biosensors

CRISPR-based biosensors possess several remarkable advantages that make them superior alternatives to conventional nucleic acid detection platforms such as PCR, ELISA, and next-generation sequencing. These advantages primarily stem from the unique molecular properties of CRISPR-associated (Cas) enzymes and their programmable specificity toward nucleic acid targets.

One of the most significant advantages is their exceptional sensitivity and specificity. Cas enzymes, such as Cas12 and Cas13, exhibit collateral cleavage activity upon target recognition, generating amplified signals that allow detection at attomolar concentrations without the need for sophisticated instrumentation (Gootenberg et al., 2017, Chen et al., 2018). The programmable nature of CRISPR RNA (crRNA) ensures high sequence fidelity, enabling the discrimination of even single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs)—a crucial feature for identifying viral mutations and antibiotic resistance genes (Patchesung et al., 2020).

A second advantage is their rapid detection capability. CRISPR-based assays can often deliver results within

30–60 minutes, compared to several hours required by PCR-based diagnostics (Broughton et al., 2020). When coupled with isothermal amplification techniques such as RPA or LAMP, these systems function effectively without thermal cyclers, enabling point-of-care testing (POCT) in resource-limited environments.

Furthermore, CRISPR biosensors offer versatility and modularity. The same detection platform can be easily reprogrammed by changing the guide RNA sequence to target new pathogens or genetic variants. This flexibility makes them ideal for pandemic preparedness and rapid response to emerging infectious diseases (Zhang et al., 2025). Multiplexing capabilities, as demonstrated in SHERLOCKv2 and HOLMESv2, further expand diagnostic throughput by allowing simultaneous detection of multiple targets in a single reaction (Zahra et al., 2023).

Another key advantage is their compatibility with simple, low-cost readout formats. CRISPR-based assays can be integrated with lateral flow strips, colorimetric systems, and smartphone-based fluorescence detectors, facilitating on-site detection without the need for complex laboratory infrastructure (Kinyua et al., 2025). This portability makes them particularly useful for field surveillance, environmental monitoring, and real-time outbreak control.

Lastly, these biosensors have demonstrated high adaptability to diverse sample types—including saliva, nasal swabs, blood, urine, and environmental samples—without significant loss of sensitivity. The integration of microfluidics and paper-based analytical devices has further improved their ease of use, scalability, and cost-effectiveness (Zu et al., 2025).

Collectively, these advantages position CRISPR-based biosensors as next-generation diagnostic tools capable of transforming molecular detection across clinical, environmental, and public health applications.

Challenges and Limitations of CRISPR-Based Biosensors

Despite their remarkable potential and rapid advancement, CRISPR-based biosensors still face several challenges that must be addressed before they can be fully integrated into mainstream diagnostic and clinical use. These limitations primarily involve issues related to sample processing, signal quantification, assay stability, and clinical translation. One of the foremost challenges is the requirement for nucleic acid pre-amplification. Although CRISPR-based assays such as SHERLOCK and DETECTR can achieve high sensitivity, they often rely on isothermal amplification methods like recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA) or loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) to reach clinically relevant detection limits (Joung et al., 2020). These additional steps not only increase assay complexity and contamination risk but also limit true

point-of-care deployment. Recent efforts to develop amplification-free CRISPR assays, such as direct Cas13-based detection (Fozouni et al., 2021), are promising but still require further optimization to match the sensitivity of amplification-dependent platforms.

Another limitation concerns quantitative accuracy. Many CRISPR-based biosensors yield qualitative or semi-quantitative results, as their signal output depends on endpoint fluorescence or visual interpretation of lateral flow assays (Kellner et al., 2019). Achieving precise and reproducible quantification remains a significant hurdle, particularly for viral load monitoring or antimicrobial resistance profiling, where exact concentration measurements are crucial. Integration with microfluidic chips, digital assays, or electrochemical readouts may help address this limitation (Hou et al., 2025).

Additionally, off-target effects and false-positive signals can compromise specificity. The high collateral cleavage activity of Cas12 and Cas13, while advantageous for signal amplification, can sometimes lead to non-specific degradation of reporter molecules (Chertow, 2018). This necessitates careful crRNA design and optimization to ensure accurate discrimination among closely related genomic sequences, especially in the case of co-infections or mixed microbial samples.

From a practical standpoint, sample preparation and matrix interference remain significant barriers. Most CRISPR-based biosensors perform best with purified nucleic acid extracts, yet direct detection in raw clinical samples such as blood, saliva, or stool often leads to reduced efficiency due to inhibitory components (Wang et al., 2025). Developing robust sample-to-answer platforms that integrate lysis, purification, and detection in a single step is essential for improving real-world applicability.

Furthermore, reagent stability and cold-chain dependence limit field deployment in low-resource settings. Many CRISPR reagents, including Cas enzymes and RNA guides, require refrigeration to maintain activity. Although lyophilization and enzyme engineering approaches have shown progress in enhancing stability, more research is needed to ensure long-term storage and transport under ambient conditions (Kaminski et al., 2021).

Lastly, there are challenges associated with regulatory approval and clinical validation. For CRISPR-based diagnostics to achieve widespread adoption, they must undergo rigorous standardization, reproducibility testing, and compliance with regulatory bodies such as the FDA or WHO. Large-scale clinical trials and cost-benefit analyses are crucial for their translation into commercial diagnostic kits.

In summary, while CRISPR-based biosensors hold great promise as transformative tools in molecular diagnostics, overcoming these technical and translational challenges will be critical for realizing their full potential in clinical medicine, field diagnostics, and global health surveillance.

Future Perspectives and Conclusion

The emergence of CRISPR-based biosensors marks a new era in molecular diagnostics, offering unprecedented opportunities for rapid, sensitive, and specific pathogen detection. As research advances, the next phase of development will focus on enhancing automation, multiplexing capacity, and field applicability to enable seamless integration into public health systems and clinical workflows.

In the near future, CRISPR biosensing platforms are expected to evolve into fully integrated “sample-to-answer” diagnostic systems. Combining microfluidic technology with CRISPR detection modules can minimize manual steps, reduce contamination risks, and shorten turnaround time (Ramachandran et al., 2020). Such lab-on-chip devices could facilitate on-site testing for infectious diseases, antimicrobial resistance, and emerging zoonotic pathogens, particularly in resource-limited settings.

Another promising direction is the integration of CRISPR diagnostics with digital and AI-based platforms. Real-time data acquisition and analysis via smartphone-based readers or IoT-enabled systems will allow remote monitoring and epidemiological surveillance (Sadique et al., 2024). These innovations will enhance early outbreak detection and response, supporting precision public health strategies.

The future of CRISPR-based biosensors will also depend on the development of novel Cas enzymes with improved efficiency, stability, and detection versatility. For instance, engineered variants of Cas12 and Cas13, as well as newer nucleases such as Cas14 and Cas Φ , exhibit unique substrate preferences and collateral activities that could expand diagnostic possibilities (Harrington et al., 2018). Additionally, amplification-free CRISPR systems, combined with nanomaterial-based signal enhancement or electrochemical transduction, are being explored to overcome current limitations in quantification and sensitivity (Mishra et al., 2023).

Efforts toward reagent stabilization and cold-chain independence will further improve accessibility and global deployment. The use of lyophilized reagents, enzyme encapsulation, and paper-based analytical devices are promising approaches to ensure reliable performance under field conditions without specialized equipment (Li et al., 2023).

Finally, as these technologies mature, standardization and regulatory validation will be essential to ensure reproducibility, safety, and accuracy. Collaborative initiatives among researchers, clinicians, and policymakers are vital to translate CRISPR biosensors from laboratory prototypes to clinically approved diagnostic tools.

In conclusion, CRISPR-based biosensors represent a transformative innovation in pathogen detection, combining molecular precision with portability and cost-

effectiveness. Continued interdisciplinary efforts in bioengineering, nanotechnology, and computational biology will accelerate their transition into mainstream diagnostics. With sustained progress, these systems are poised to become next-generation diagnostic platforms that can revolutionize disease surveillance, outbreak control, and personalized medicine across the globe.

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